

An Experimental Contribution to the Theory of Equation of State for Adsorbed Substances.

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If one considers with Langmuir $(\sigma_0 - \sigma) = \pi$ as the two dimensional osmotic pressure of the dissolved substance on the surface, then according to Volmer (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1925, 250, cf. also Adams, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1922, A 101, 526), one can deduce a characteristic equation for adsorbed substances which from the measurements of adsorption of benzophenone on mercury has been found to take the following form :

$$\pi (\Omega - \beta) = RT \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where Ω = the surface which contains a gram molecule of the dissolved capillar-active substance.

β = a correction-factor, i.e., twice the surface actually occupied by a gram-molecule of the dissolved substance.

Assuming $\frac{\beta}{\Omega}$ to be very small compared to 2, Volmer (*loc. cit.*) also obtained the following relation between π and c :—

$$\pi = \frac{RTc}{k + \beta c} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{1}{\Omega} = \frac{c}{k + 2\beta c} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Integrating the well known Gibb's equation (Milner, *Phil. Mag.*, 1907, 23, 96) one obtains the following equation which has already been found empirically by Szyzkowski (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1908, 64, 392) :—

$$\pi = \frac{RT}{2\beta} \ln \left(\frac{2\beta c}{k} + 1 \right) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

If one accepts equation (1) to be sufficiently correct, then equations (3) and (4) assume the character of approximations. If equation is

used without neglecting the higher powers of $\left(\frac{\beta}{\Omega}\right)$, then we have, from (1) and the Gibb's equation,

$$RT \frac{dc}{c} = RT \frac{d\pi}{\pi} + \beta d\pi,$$

which on integration gives

$$RT \ln c + \beta = RT \ln \pi + \beta\pi \quad (5)$$

The present work deals with general validity of equation (2) which has been found to hold good in the case of saturation of mercury with benzophenone.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The surface tensions were measured by a modified form of the method used by Sugden (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 121, 1). [Schroedinger equation (*Ann. Phys.*, 1915, [IV], 45, 413)].

A capillary tube (K) with the end cut as sharply as possible is dipped in the liquid, and the maximum pressure of the gas (air or a suitable indifferent gas) at the exit of the bubble is measured. A sketch of the arrangement used is given in Fig. I.

P and G contain the solution and W contains water. Behind the vertical U-tube M, containing a dilute coloured solution is attached a millimeter scale to read the difference in level between the two arms of the tube. The height of the solution above the capillary end K is read with a cathetometer. G is detachable at S and R being provided with ground in glass joints. The capillary tube is fused into a wider tube which fits exactly into the ground in joint at R. When cock L is closed and H opened, water flows out of W, a partial vacuum is created and air enters into P gets saturated with the vapour of the solution, and bubbles through the capillary tube. The maximum pressure difference is proportional to $h = h_w - h_s$, where $h_w =$ the reading of water manometer and $h_s =$ height of the solution as measured by the cathetometer. The capillary-end must be made as far as possible circular in shape and very sharply cut. The diameter as measured by micrometer was found to be about 0.0048 cm.

FIG. 1.

Fig. 2.

To ascertain that the capillary opening has not been enlarged by gradual solution of the glass or narrowed down by any impurity, measurements of the surface tension of pure water and benzene are carried out before every series of experiments. A new capillary made and its shape and diameter measured where necessary. The smallness of the capillary allowed a level-difference, h_m , of 480 to 630.5 mm. and under these circumstances, the terms containing the factor (r/h) in Schrodinger's equation may be neglected.

But in the case of solutions of capillar-active substances the maximum pressure sinks slowly down, while the number of bubbles coming out per unit time decreases. If the air within the bubble is assumed to be saturated with the vapour of the solution, the cause for this slow establishment of equilibrium must be attributed to the fact that the formation of the bubble dilutes the surrounding solution through adsorption of the solute and the next bubble has a poorer solution around it. The original concentration is reached slowly as is well known. Similar relations have been observed in the case of drop-electrodes. In every case readings were taken with decreasing number of bubbles in a given interval and the limiting value for infinitely slow formation of bubbles was obtained by extrapolation.

In this work ordinary distilled water has been used throughout. The chemicals used in this investigation were obtained from Kahlbaum. The fatty acids were subjected to fractional distillation and their purity tested.

Results and Discussions.

Volmer (*loc. cit.*) states that at small concentrations equations (2) and (4) are identical. Equation (4) may be written as:—

$$\begin{aligned} \pi &= \frac{RT}{2\beta} \ln \left(\frac{2\beta c}{k} + 1 \right) \\ &= \frac{RT}{2\beta} \left[\frac{2\beta c}{k} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2\beta c}{k} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{2\beta c}{k} \right)^3 \dots \dots \dots \right] \\ &= \frac{RTc}{k(1 + \frac{\beta c}{k})} + \frac{RTc}{k} \left[\frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{\beta c}{k} \right)^2 \dots \dots \dots \right] \\ &= \frac{RTc}{k + \beta c} + \frac{RTc}{k} \left[\frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{\beta c}{k} \right)^2 \dots \dots \dots \right] \end{aligned}$$

If $\frac{\beta_0}{k}$ be not very small, then the values of π according to (4)

are greater than those derived from (2). In the following Tables (I-VI), π is calculated by a method of approximation (to be discussed later) according to both these equations. The surface tensions are expressed in dynes cm. and concentration in gram-mol litre.

TABLE I.

n-Butyric Acid.

(Szyzkowski—20°)

$$\beta = 5.82 \times 10^8; k = 1.5 \times 10^8; T = 72.66.$$

Concentration.	π observed.	π calc. (Eq. 2).	π calc. (Eq. 4).
0.0242	4.26	4.55	4.563
0.0363	6.50	6.47	6.54
0.0545	9.01	9.09	9.15
0.0917	12.21	12.23	12.53
0.122	15.81	15.92	16.77
0.184	19.95	20.17	21.95
0.276	24.27	24.3	27.8
0.414	28.92	28.3	34.4
0.6205	33.75	31.7	41.4

TABLE II.

n-Valeric Acid (17.5°).

$$\beta = 4.65 \times 10^8; k = 0.394 \times 10^8; T = 72.9.$$

Concentration.	π observed.	π calc. (Eq. 2).	π calc. (Eq. 4).
0.0093	5.1	5.14	5.18
0.014	7.4	7.26	7.46
0.021	10.8	10.6	10.54
0.0315	14.5	14.05	14.57
0.0475	18.95	18.7	19.72
0.071	23.3	23.7	25.75
0.107	28.2	29.0	33.2
0.160	33.2	33.9	41.0
0.240	38.3	38.5	49.6

TABLE III.

n-Hexylio Acid.

$t = 18^\circ - 19^\circ$; $\delta_0 = 72.66$; $\beta = 4.8 \times 10^5$; $k = 0.129 \times 10^5$.

Concentration.	π observed.	π calc. (Eq. 2).	π calc. (Eq. 4).
0.00425	9.16	6.98	6.95
0.0064	9.66	9.9	9.97
0.0085	12.56	12.45	12.55
0.0128	17.26	16.85	17.24
0.0170	21.01	20.4	21.22
0.0212	23.66	23.32	24.63
0.0256	25.84	25.98	27.83
0.0340	29.91	29.99	33.1
0.0425	32.96	33.0	37.53
0.051	35.41	35.5	41.45
0.068	38.46	39.2	47.83
0.085	41.86	41.7	53.04

TABLE IV.

n-Heptylio Acid.

$t = 19^\circ \text{C}$, therefore $\delta_0 = 72.66$; $\beta = 4.74 \times 10^5$; $k = 0.0291 \times 10^5$.

Concentration.	π observed.	π calc. (Eq. 2).	π calc. (Eq. 4).
0.001059	5.96	7.52	7.92
0.00254	14.91	14.98	15.95
0.00381	19.76	19.6	20.65
0.004887	22.79	22.7	24.84
0.00588	24.98	25.08	27.8
0.00678	25.76	26.82	29.5
0.007775	28.46	28.5	32.3
0.008825	30.06	30.12	34.5
0.01089	32.56	32.4	38.2

TABLE V.

n-Octylo Acid.

$t=24^{\circ}\text{C}$, therefore $\delta_0=71.93$; $\beta=4.105 \times 10^3$; $k=0.01016 \times 10^3$

Concentration.	π observed.	π calc. (Eq. 2).	π calc. (Eq. 4).
0.0008861	6.49	7.18	7.8
0.0006722	13.43	13.08	13.13
0.0010083	17.68	17.4	18.12
0.001844	21.03	21.18	22.24
0.001680	23.93	24.3	26.0
0.0020166	26.48	27.0	29.3
0.002352	28.9	29.33	32.25
0.002688	31.18	31.3	35.0
0.003025	33.23	33.1	37.5
0.003361	34.83	34.64	39.8

TABLE VI.

n-Nonylic Acid.

$t=19^{\circ}\text{C}$, therefore $\delta_0=72.66$; $\beta=3.61 \times 10^3$; $k=0.00286 \times 10^3$.

Concentration.	π observed.	π calc. (Eq. 2).	π calc. (Eq. 4).
0.0001520	9.16	10.88	10.96
0.000293	15.03	15.2	15.4
0.0003862	22.04	22.02	22.95
0.0004778	25.63	25.8	26.6
0.000545	27.39	27.4	29.3
0.000637	29.94	29.93	32.3
0.0007645	33.03	33.0	36.2
0.000695	31.48	31.4	34.0

From these tables we see that (2) and (4) are practically identical at small concentrations, but at higher concentrations they differ from one another.

In fact $\left(\frac{\beta c}{k}\right)$ reaches values greater than 1 at higher concentrations, and therefore in those cases the equations are not applicable. Table VII in which values of $\left(\frac{\beta c}{k}\right)$ for two approximately equal values of π are given, will make it clearer.

TABLE VII.

Substance.	$\beta \times 10^{-3}$	$k \times 10^{-5}$	$\frac{\beta c}{k}$					
			(Conc.) ₁	π_1	$\left(\frac{\beta c}{k}\right)_1$	Conc. ₂	π_2	$\left(\frac{\beta c}{k}\right)_2$
n-Butyric acid	5.82	1.15	0.0363	6.5	0.184	0.6205	33.75	8.14
n-Valeric acid	4.65	0.394	0.0093	5.1	0.1099	0.160	33.2	1.86
n-Hexylic acid	4.3	0.129	0.00425	6.16	0.1415	0.0425	32.86	1.415
n-Heptylic acid	4.74	0.0291	0.001059	5.96	0.1448	0.01089	32.56	1.53
n-Octylic acid	4.105	0.01016	0.0003861	6.43	0.1357	0.003025	33.23	1.223
n-Nonylic acid	3.61	0.00286	0.000152	9.16	0.193	0.0007645	33.03	0.965

In the case of higher fatty acids with little solubility the agreement between these two equations for all concentrations is certainly better but still not satisfactory.

The area occupied by the molecules adsorbed on the surface can be calculated from the above only from the observations at low concentrations. Such observations are not however as accurate as those at higher concentrations. Moreover, at very low concentrations, where in the adsorption layer the ideal gas laws almost hold good, the influence of β is negligible and consequently it cannot be measured accurately. The actual area occupied by the molecule was for these reasons calculated according to the more rigorous equation. For the calculation of α and β , the following method of approximation was used:

First of all, from the measurements at two successive concentrations β was calculated according to the equation,

$$\beta_1 = \frac{RT}{\pi_2 - \pi_1} \ln \left(\frac{c_2 \pi_1}{c_1 \pi_2} \right).$$

then from all these values of β , the mean value β_2 was taken. With this β_2 , from the following equation, the values of α was calculated.

$$\alpha = RT \ln \frac{\pi}{c} + \beta_2 \pi$$

From these values of α , the mean value α_s was taken and then the mean value of β (β_s) was once more calculated.

From these values of α and β the corresponding concentrations were calculated from the observed values of π according to equation

$$\ln c = \frac{RT \ln \pi + \beta_s \pi - \alpha_s}{RT}$$

and the differences were graphically determined.

It is found that the values of π thus calculated show good agreement with those obtained for the following solutions: (1) acetic acid, propionic acid (Drucker, *Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1905, 52, 648); (2) propionic acid (Rehbinder, *ibid.*, 1924, 111, 447); (3) *n*-butyric acid, *n*-valeric acid, *n*-hexylic acid (Szyzkowski, *loc. cit.*); (4) *n*-heptylic acid, *n*-octylic acid, *n*-nonylic acid (Roy, *vide supra*).

We have also determined the surface tension of solutions of the substances mentioned in the following tables where the values of π observed with those calculated from equation (5) are also given:

TABLE VIII.

Monomethylurea.

$$t = 21^\circ\text{C}; \alpha = 2.2445 \times 10^{10}; \beta = 12.24 \times 10^6.$$

Conc.	σ obs.	π obs.	π calc.	Conc. calc.
0.00	72.37	0.00
1.238	69.6	2.77	2.77	1.267
1.63	68.93	3.44	3.54	1.628
2.09	68.12	4.25	4.25	2.088
2.61	67.3	5.07	5.07	2.608

TABLE IX.

Symmetrical Dimethylurea.

$$t = 20^{\circ}\text{C}; \alpha = 5.06 \times 10^{10}; \beta = 18.5 \times 10^6.$$

Conc.	σ obs.	π obs.	π calc.	Conc. calc.
0.00	72.58	0.00
0.2675	70.3	2.28	2.08	0.2959
0.535	69.2	3.93	3.38	0.5354
0.767	68.2	4.38	4.38	0.753
1.0704	67.0	5.53	5.63	1.049
1.504	65.5	7.03	7.03	1.503
1.935	63.6	8.93	9.08	2.096

TABLE X.

Ethylurea.

$$t = 19.5^{\circ}\text{C}; \alpha = 6.29 \times 10^{10}; \beta = 9.04 \times 10^6.$$

Conc.	σ obs.	π obs.	π calc.	Conc. calc.
0.00	72.66	0.00
0.2735	69.6	3.06	3.2	0.2524
0.547	66.86	5.75	5.85	0.4247
0.82	64.5	6.1	6.1	0.825
1.23	61.4	11.2	10.9	1.276
1.846	58.0	14.6	14.3	1.895
2.585	55.1	17.5	17.6	2.52

TABLE XI.

Symmetrical Diethylurea.

$$t = 19.5^{\circ}\text{C}; \alpha = 10.14 \times 10^{10}; \beta = 14.7 \times 10^8.$$

Conc.	σ obs.	π obs.	π calc.	Conc. calc.	
0.00	72.6	0.00	
0.0461	70.0	2.6		0.0468	
0.09026	67.9	4.7		0.096	
0.1805	65.4	7.2		0.1706	
0.2344	63.7	8.0	Almost the same values as those observed.	0.235	
0.306	62.15	10.45		0.3023	
0.4032	60.32	12.28		0.3066	
0.524	58.4	14.2		0.516	
0.661	56.15	16.46		0.683	
0.8173	55.2	18.4		18.0	0.861

TABLE XII.

Phenol.

$$t = 19^{\circ}\text{C}; \alpha = 12.8 \times 10^{10}; \beta = 10.24 \times 10^8.$$

Conc.	σ obs.	π obs.	π calc.	Conc. calc.
0.00	72.66	0.00
0.02505	69.75	2.91	4.26	0.0166
0.0501	66.4	6.26	7.26	0.0413
0.084	62.1	10.56	10.56	0.0834
0.1002	60.7	11.78	11.96	0.1000
0.1252	58.9	13.96	13.76	0.1247
0.1606	56.6	16.06	16.06	0.1609
0.1841	65.2	17.46	17.46	0.1802
0.2087	63.6	19.06	18.76	0.2155
0.2504	61.2	21.46	20.66	0.2706

Fig. 3.

From the above we see that in the case of lower fatty acids, the agreement between the values calculated according to the equation (5) and those observed are satisfactory up to middle concentrations. For the higher homologues with decreasing solubility the agreement between these values are satisfactory up to the highest concentrations studied. Also we find that in the case of the higher fatty acids, no matter according to which equation the values of π are calculated, the tension at lower concentrations are always greater than those calculated (*vide* Fig. 2, for *n*-butyric and *n*-nonylic acid). The (σ , conc.) curve has bend in that region. This anomaly which has also been noticed by Lord Raleigh (*Phil. Mag.*, 1889, 48, 881) and Langmuir cannot possibly be due simply to errors in experiments. That this effect depends only on the electrolytic dissociation, which at smaller concentrations must reach its maximum, appears also doubtful.

The equations derived in the introduction contain definite physical significance through the experimentally settled fact that the adsorption-layer is only one molecule thick. On this assumption β of Van der Waal's equation is to be considered in this case as double the cross-section of the adsorbed molecule. The molecular cross sections (f) as calculated from the experimental results are put together in the following table:—

$$f = \frac{\beta}{2N}, \text{ where } N = 6.06 \times 10^{23}$$

TABLE XIII.

			$\beta \times 10^{-8}$ (Eq. 5)	$f \times 10^{16}$
Acetic acid	16.4	13.52
Propionic acid	18.95	11.51
<i>n</i> -Butyric acid	10.7	8.83
<i>n</i> -Valeric acid	10.01	8.26
<i>n</i> -Hexylic acid	10.4	8.58
<i>n</i> -Heptylic acid	10.04	8.3
<i>n</i> -Octylic acid	7.54	6.26
<i>n</i> -Nonylic acid	6.00	4.95
Monomethyl urea	12.24	10.1
Symmetrical dimethyl urea	18.5	15.25
Ethyl urea	11.25	9.28
Symmetrical diethyl urea	14.7	12.12
Phenol	10.24	8.45

From Table XIII we observe that the effective molecular cross section of the normal fatty acids in the adsorption layer does not increase with increasing molecular weights. Langmuir thinks that this constant magnitude of the area occupied by the fatty acids is to be explained by the vertical position of the carbon chain in the

surface. This supposition is more strikingly confirmed by our results with urea derivatives. If one agrees with Langmuir and Harkins that the group containing oxygen is directed downwards in the water while the hydrocarbon groups are pointed towards surface, one can easily explain the increase of the value of f when one passes from monomethylurea to *s*-dimethylurea. Then the values of (f) in the case of methylurea and ethylurea must also be the same, which agrees with our experimental results.

The term a has the same significance as an integration constant as the term k in the equation (2) i.e., it controls the distribution relation between the number of molecules in the solution and in the surface. One can certainly according to the method of Langmuir convince oneself of this that a differs from the adsorption potential A by the same additive constant for all substances dissolved in the same solvent, the magnitude of which depends on the thickness of the adsorption layer.

Langmuir has drawn our attention to the fact that Traube's Law is equivalent to the increase of the adsorption potential in the arithmetic progression, if the area occupied by the molecule in the homologous series is constant. We find in our experimental results a further confirmation of Traube's Law. But it remains as yet unexplained, why A increases by the same amount as we go up in the homologous series (*vide* Table XIII.) We would venture a suggestion that because of the polar character of the fatty acids, the adsorption potential must be proportional to the dipol-moment of the molecule, and therefore increases by jumps with the length of the carbon chain as would appear from Table XIV.

TABLE XIV.

			$a \times 10^{-10}$ (Eq. 5)	$\Delta a \times 10^{-10}$
Acetic acid	8.75	
Propionic acid	11.80	2.15
<i>n</i> -Butyric acid	13.85	2.05
<i>n</i> -Valeric acid	16.23	2.88
<i>n</i> -Hexylic acid	19.40	3.17
<i>n</i> -Heptylic acid	22.7	3.8
<i>n</i> -Octylic acid	26.42	2.72
<i>n</i> -Nonylic acid	27.78	2.86

From these investigations we can conclude that the equation for adsorbed substances proposed by Volmer is applicable to solutions up to moderate concentrations within the range of experimental error and that this equation allows us with fair approximation to consider the area occupied by the molecules of the solute on the surface of the solution and also the adsorption potential as independent of concentration.

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